

Design an Underwater Passive Target Tracking Model Using DeeTtention Technique for Noisy Ocean Environment

Sumonto Sarker^{1,*}, Rakibul Islam¹, Md. Humaun Kabir¹

¹Department of ECE, Hajee Mohammad Danesh Science and Technology University, Dinajpur

*Corresponding author: sumonto@hstu.ac.bd

Abstract— This paper proposes DeeTtention, a DeepCNN–TCN model with Self-Attention and Cross-Attention for underwater passive target tracking. Synthetic datasets based on Constant Velocity and Coordinated Turn motion models are used. The proposed model is compared with EKF and CNN-LSTM-Attention. Results show significant improvement in tracking accuracy and trajectory prediction.

Keywords— Target Tracking, CNN, TCN, Self- Attention, Cross-Attention, Deep Learning, Complex Motion Prediction, Contextual Feature Extraction, EKF, Passive Target Tracking.

I. Introduction

Underwater target tracking is important for defense, surveillance, and marine research. Traditional filters such as EKF suffer in highly nonlinear environments. UKF, PF, UPF also have some particular problem. Deep learning methods can learn complex motion patterns directly from data. This work introduces DeeTtention to improve tracking performance in noisy and maneuvering scenarios. The method is tested for tracking targets on straight and turning paths, showing improved performance in comparison with conventional Gaussian filters in terms of RMSE.

II. Methodology

The proposed underwater passive target tracking framework consists of five major stages: synthetic data generation, data preprocessing, deep learning model development, training, and performance evaluation. A synthetic dataset is generated using Constant Velocity (CV) and Coordinated Turn (CT) motion models to simulate realistic underwater target trajectories under different maneuvering conditions

A. Experimental Setup

Fig-1: The Architecture of proposed model

Process noise and measurement noise are incorporated to emulate environmental uncertainties and sensor imperfections. The target state vector is represented as

$$X_k = [x_k, y_k, v_{x,k}, v_{y,k}, \omega_k]^T \quad (1)$$

where x_k and y_k denote target position, $v_{x,k}$ and $v_{y,k}$ represent velocity components, and ω_k is the angular velocity. For straight-line motion, the state update equations are

$$x_{k+1} = x_k + v_x \Delta t \quad (2)$$

$$y_{k+1} = y_k + v_y \Delta t \quad (3)$$

After trajectory generation, Gaussian measurement noise is added to obtain noisy observations. A sliding-window technique is then employed to transform the sequential measurements into supervised learning samples. A sequence of past observations is used as input, while the subsequent true position serves as the prediction target.

B. Signal Processing

The proposed DeeTtention architecture integrates Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DeepCNN), Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN), Self-Attention, and Cross-Attention mechanisms. The DeepCNN extracts local spatial features from the input sequence, while the TCN captures long-range temporal dependencies. The attention mechanism is defined as

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{Softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (4)$$

which enables the network to focus on the most relevant temporal features. Self-Attention captures internal sequence relationships, whereas Cross-Attention incorporates global contextual information to improve trajectory prediction accuracy. The network is trained using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss function and optimized using the Adam optimizer. Model performance is evaluated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE).

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\hat{y}_i - y_i|^2 \right\}} \quad (5)$$

where lower RMSE values indicate superior tracking accuracy. The proposed DeeTtention model is compared with the Extended

Kalman Filter (EKF) and CNN-LSTM-Attention models under multiple maneuvering scenarios.

III. Simulation Result and Discussion

Fig-2: Three maneuvering scenarios (simple, moderate, and highly maneuvering)

Fig-3: RMSE Comparison of EKF, CLA, DeeTention Model for Three maneuvering.

Three maneuvering scenarios (simple, moderate, and highly maneuvering) were evaluated. DeeTention achieved RMSE values of approximately 2.11, 4.87, and 5.61 respectively, outperforming CNN-LSTM-Attention and EKF in all cases. The proposed model accurately follows target trajectories and maintains robustness under complex motion patterns. Attention mechanisms help preserve global context, while TCN effectively captures temporal dependencies. EKF performance degrades significantly in nonlinear scenarios.

IV. Conclusion

DeeTention provides highly accurate underwater passive target tracking and state estimation. The combination of DeepCNN, TCN, Self-Attention, and Cross-Attention substantially reduces tracking error compared with conventional filtering and existing deep-learning approaches.

References

- [1] J. Luo, Y. Han, and L. Fan, "Underwater Acoustic Target Tracking: A Review," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. 112, 2018. doi: 10.3390/s18010112.
- [2] Q. Li and Q. Ma, "Underwater Passive Target Detection Fusion Based on Distributed Acoustic Sensor Network," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing (ICSPCC)*, Xi'an, China, 2021, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/ICSPCC52875.2021.9564522.